

COMPARISON OF PERMEATION BEHAVIOR OF ACID SOLUTION AND VAPOR INTO POLYAMIDE 66

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SUMMARY: The behavior or permeability of environmental solution pass through the polymeric materials is one of critical factor, especially when polymeric material is used for corrosion protection. In this research, the study on penetration/permeation behavior of acid solution and vapor was carried out and to be an objective. Permeation test was done by setting the specimen in stagnant acid solution-deionized water and acid vapor-air condition. Permeation behavior of acid solution and vapor (HCl) into polyamide 66 showed the different behavior. The differences are not only on its diffusivity into PA66 but also to the distribution of Cl element in PA66. Both of penetration/permeation of acid solution and acid vapor (HCl) into PA66 follow the Fickian diffusion. In this case, diffusion rate of acid solution in liquid phase is faster than its vapor from the same solution. Anion of acid solution takes part in PA66 degradation.

KEYWORDS: diffusion, polyamide, acid vapor, degradation, molecular weight, permeation

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, polymeric materials are widely used for many aspects. Generally, the lifetimes of materials are directly related to the environments. Once a penetrant is introduced into polymeric materials, it may lead to a variety of chemical and physical changes in the material, e.g. plasticization and swelling. These changes may affect its durability performance in application as engineering plastics, chemical equipment materials (e.g. a storage tank), medicine field, and etc [1-2]. Several studies have been published on the diffusion of environment solutions into polyamide and degradation of polyamide in acid environments [3-6]. We have reported that polyamide was convenient test material for discussing corrosion process due to its hydrophilicity and reaction with acid, moreover, because PA66 was degraded with comparable level of diffusion and reaction rate [7-8]. Therefore the degradation of the polymeric materials could be generally simulated. Thus polyamide 66 was used as test material in this study.

The behavior or permeability of environmental solution pass through the polymeric materials is one of critical factor, especially when polymeric material is used for corrosion protection. In few years, there were some incidents occurred in the acid FRP storage tank which resulted in an escape or leak-age of the stored liquid. In some cases, the failure of the tank roof which had no contact with acid liquid occurred and caused any injuries or casualties. Some investigations have been done in order to know the cause of failure but there are still insufficient information related to the permeation behavior of acid solution and vapor, especially in case when vapor condense during the diffusion process. Therefore in this

research, the study on penetration/permeation behavior of acid solution and vapor was carried out and to be an objective.

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Experimental methods

Permeation behavior of acid solution and vapor into polyamide 66 were studied in this research. Generally, penetrants diffusion in polymers may be determined by standard techniques conventionally used for investigating the solubility and diffusion of low-molecular weight compounds in polymers. Measuring the weight change of sample is one of the common method and technique which familiar being used. The variations of sample weight will be due to the sorption of water and penetrant molecules. This method of measurement was applied in this research.

a. Material and condition

A commercially polyamide 66 (PA 66, UBE 2020) was used as test material in the present study. The specimen geometry for penetration test was 60 x 60 mm with 2 mm thickness. Hydrochloric acid solution of 10 wt % was used as environmental solution for permeation test of acid solution. In addition, vapor of hydrochloric acid solution of 10 wt %, 20 wt % (partial pressure (p) of HCl vapor over aqueous solution of HCl 20 wt %, $p_{\text{HCl}} = 1.55 \text{ mmHg}$ and partial pressure of water over aqueous solution of HCl 20 wt %, $p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 43.6 \text{ mmHg}$) and 35 wt % ($p_{\text{HCl}} = 211 \text{ mmHg}$, $p_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 15.4 \text{ mmHg}$) at 45°C were applied for vapor test [9].

b. Penetration test

Permeation test was done by setting the specimen in stagnant acid solution-deionized water and acid vapor-air condition as shown in Fig.1(a) and (b). One side was contacted with the acid solution/vapor and the opposite side was with the deionised water/air, respectively (Fig.1 (a) and (b)). Temperature at both sides was set to be same at 50°C for permeation test of acid solution and controlled automatically by using temperature sensor which connected to the heater. On the other hand for vapor test, the both temperature of HCl vapor and air were set at 45°C (Fig.1 (b))

Fig.1 Schematic diagram of the penetration test (a) Liquid/solution test, one side was contacted to the penetrant (acid solution) and water at the opposite side (b) vapor test, one side was contacted with acid vapor and air at the opposite side.

c. Penetration/diffusion analysis

Penetration/permeation analysis was done by measuring weight change and penetration depth of chlorine (Cl) element by using energy dispersive x-ray spectrometer (EDS). Specimen was placed into condition as shown in Fig.1 (a) and (b), and then specimen was removed after regular time, carefully wiped to remove excess penetrant. Specimen was put in room temperature for 1 hour before its weight was measured. Specimen was weighed using microbalance.

Fig. 2 Penetration/permeation area on polyamide 66 specimen.

The penetrant uptake is determined by obtaining the change in mass of specimen at different times, relatives to the initial mass. The important thing to be noted, penetration/ permeation area is not all the surface of specimen as shown in Fig.2. If the area of specimen is described as A_o and penetration/permeation area is A_p , weight change (%W) is formulated as follows;

$$\%W = \frac{M_s - M_o}{M_o \times \frac{A_p}{A_o}} \times 100 \% \quad (1)$$

where M_o (g) is specimen weight before penetration/permeation test, M_s (g) is specimen weight after penetration test.

Penetration depth of chlorine (Cl) element in this research was monitored by combination of scanning electron microscope (SEM) and X-ray micro analysis (EDS) on cross section of PA66. EDS results described the distribution of chlorine element in PA 66, and penetration depth of sulfur or chlorine was determined from this profile.

d. Degradation analysis

The degree of PA 66 degradation was evaluated by decrease of molecular weight. In this research, SEC (Size Exclusion Chromatography) was used to observed degradation of PA 66. The solvent which used for analysis was the mixture of m-cresol/chloroform with composition 35/65 weight percent which also as the mobile phase of SEC system. PA 66 was dissolved by m-cresol in this mixture.

Sample from degraded PA66 was taken about 20 mg at the specific thickness (0.1~0.2 mm of thickness) for injection, and then this sample was dissolved into 10 ml of m-cresol/chloroform mixture with composition 35/65 weight percent for almost 2 hours This mixture was filtered and then injected into chromatodisk. Sample introduced into solvent stream going through the column ($T=40^{\circ}C$) with the flow rate 0.5 ml/min.

Results and discussion

a. Permeation behavior of acid solution and vapor

The comparison between permeation behavior of acid solution and vapor has been observed. In addition, degradation behavior also has been studied in these two-environment conditions. Permeation of acid solution has been studied systematically with sulfuric acid solution as environmental solution in our previous work. It was concluded that the permeation mechanism could be observed as follows; at first water penetrated into polyamide and then it was followed by acid. In this process (temperature 50°C), water didn't affect the change of molecular weight but only reduced the polyamide strength by plasticization. Moreover, proton (H^+) had contribution to the anion transport and degradation of polyamide by the hydrolytic reaction. We found that the anion of acid could not diffuse into polyamide 66 without the presence of proton. In the term of the hydrolytic reaction, proton attacked the polyamide chain and scission of chains occurred. This affected the reducing of molecular size and the loss of polyamide strength significantly. This conclusion can be clearly obtained from the measurement penetration depth of anion (element by using Energy Dispersive X-Ray Spectrometer) and molecular weight (by using Size Exclusion Chromatography) of polyamide 66 specimens. The pH and ion concentration measurement were also performed in order to study the behavior of ion mobility.

Permeation behavior of acid vapor was also observed with the same method as acid solution by measuring the weight change of PA66. Figure 3(a) shows the weight change of PA66 after contacted with HCl 10 wt % solution and vapor of HCl 20 wt % solutions. As can be observed, the sorption amount of HCl 10 wt % solution is higher than vapor of HCl 20 wt % solution. It is probably due to the degree of swelling of PA66 in acid solution was higher than vapor condition or higher density and direct contact of liquid phase can immediately fill the free volume of PA66. Therefore HCl solution reached to the maximum weight uptake or weight change faster than vapor condition as shown in Fig.3(a). Figure 3(b) shows the weight change of PA66 with square root time. The straight line can be fitted well on the data. It means that diffusion of both HCl solution and vapor follow the Fickian's law [10]. This result also gives the good agreement with our previous works with sulfuric acid solution in liquid phase [7-8].

Fig. 3. Weight change of HCl 20 wt % vapor, HCl 10 wt % solution and HCl 10 wt % vapor after permeation test (a) by time (b) by square root time.

The diffusion followed the Fickian's law at the beginning of diffusion period. We have observed that on study of sulfuric acid solution diffusion, when crack occurs due to degradation of PA66, the diffusion will not follow the Fickian' law due to the significant

increase of amount of acid sorption. Crack make the resistant of PA66 to the environmental solution or vapor diffusion reduce significantly.

Penetration depth of acid solution and vapor element was observed by using EDS. Figure 4(a) is one example of EDS analysis results on cross section area of PA66 which contacted to the acid vapor. Penetration depth of Cl element was determined from EDS results by visually as shown in Fig.4(a). Penetration depth measurement for other data was given in Fig.4(b). It is observed that, the penetration depth of Cl element of vapor of HCl 20 wt % solution is lower than HCl 10 wt % solution, whereas for weight change relation in Fig.3 also shows the same trend. High sorption of HCl 10 wt % solution in Fig. 3 was probably mainly obtained by water diffusion. On the other hand, high penetration depth of Cl element of HCl 10 wt % might be caused by the swelling of PA66 and uniformity of HCl solution diffusion on surface of PA66. In addition, penetration depth of vapor of HCl 10 wt % solution was also measured, but the presence of Cl element was not detected by EDS due to the very low concentration of HCl in vapor condition. Moreover, the measurement of penetration depth of HCl 20 wt % solution for 3 hours contact time was also performed. It was observed the penetration depth of Cl element is approximately $x/L = 0.85$ that of higher than vapor condition ($x/L = 0.0753$) on the same time. Thus permeation rate of HCl vapor from HCl solution is slower than it solution itself. Unfortunately, penetration depth of Cl element for longer contact time could not be measured due to dissolving of PA66 by HCl 20 wt % solution.

Fig. 4. Penetration depth of Cl element into PA66 (a) Determining method for penetration depth of Cl from EDS results (b) Penetration depth of Cl element of HCl 20 wt % solution and HCl 10 wt % vapor which got from EDS measurement and determined visually as explained in (a).

Permeation behavior of acid solution and vapor (HCl) into polyamide 66 showed the different behavior. The difference is not only on the sorption ability but also to the distribution of Cl element in PA66. It can be observed from Fig.5 which shows the concentration profile of acid solution and acid vapor in PA66. Result of vapor of HCl 35 wt % solution for 6 hours contact time and data of HCl 10 wt % solution for 24 hours contact time were used for this comparison. In this case, we just want to compare the concentration/distribution profile of Cl element in PA66 without consider the diffusion rate of HCl solution. From this comparison, concentration profile of the acid solution shows trend of continuous gradient. On the other hand, discontinuous gradation of concentration of the vapor acid in PA66 was recognized. This difference can be observed clearly when used vapor of HCl 35 wt %, whereas for vapor of HCl 20 wt % is very difficult to observed due to few amount of HCl vapor in equilibrium with water moisture compare to the HCl 35 wt % solution. The concentration of Cl element of HCl solution in Fig.5 (a) was plotted into Fig.5(b) in order to compare the differences. As can

be observed, totally, there is a kind of two parts of Cl element distribution in PA66 after contacted with acid vapor. It can be considered that in the vapor condition, the observed concentration was combination of acid vapor and solution which condensed during the diffusion process. Some of acid vapor was condensed when contact to the polyamide surface and during the diffusion. Although the phase of some acid vapor was changed from vapor into liquid, this condensed acid continued the diffusion together with uncondensed acid vapor along the polyamide with the different diffusion rate.

Fig.5 Concentration profile of Cl element in the cross section of PA66 specimen (a) after contact with 10 wt % HCl solution, 50°C (b) after contact with HCl vapor (vapor of 35 wt % HCl solution, 45°C)

b. Degradation of PA66 by acid solution and vapor

Degradation of PA66 was discussed systematically by analyzing the decrease of average molecular weight after contacted with acid solution. In order to compare the degradation of PA66 after contacted with acid solution and acid vapor, HCl solution and vapor of HCl solution was used as environment condition. The change of average molecular weight was shown in Fig. 6 (a) and (b). Average molecular weight distribution was plotted with ratio of average molecular weight before and after penetration/permeation test. The decrease of molecular weight could be observed clearly by using this ratio as shown in Fig. 6(a) and (b). Molecular weight of PA 66 decreased from the HCl solution or HCl vapor side with contact time. The change of average molecular weight by HCl solution shows the same profile as our results when worked with H₂SO₄ solution. The reducing of average molecular weight by H₂SO₄ solution was performed in Fig. 7(a). Average molecular weight reduced as decreasing of acid concentration in PA66. Reducing of average molecular size would affect not only to the loss of PA66 strength but also probably to the increase of the diffusion rate of acid solution. The diffusion rate would increase significantly if crack growth and propagate. In crack region, it was assumed that there is an insignificant resistance to flow of penetrant. So it has very high diffusion rate. Some reports showed that at crack region of polymer, the diffusion rate is predicted to be constant [11-12]. From this explanation, degradation of PA66 affects the diffusion rate of acid solution.

The degradation of molecular weight at the specific positions in PA 66 (defined as x/L) along the thickness shows the different level with contact time as shown in Fig. 7(b). Average molecular weight near surface which contacted with acid decrease sharply with time increase.

These differences were caused by distribution or concentration of acid in PA 66. Concentration of acid near the surface was higher than other place along PA 66 thickness. Therefore degradation of PA 66 near surface was more significant due to the high reaction rate, whereas if far from the acid side, the degradation rate then reduced as decreasing of acid concentration along PA 66 thickness. The decrease of molecular weight related to the degradation of polyamide due to chemical reaction by acid hydrolysis [13-15]. It indicated that chains scission occurred in PA 66.

Fig. 6 Comparison of penetration depth of Cl element and average molecular weight distribution of polyamide 66 between HCl solution and vapor of HCl solution along the thickness after permeation test for 24 hours (a) in 10 wt % HCl solution – water at 50°C (b) in vapor of 20 wt % HCl solution – air at 45°C.

Relation between penetration depth of anion and degradation of PA66, which in this case was defined by decreasing of average of molecular weight, was observed as shown in Fig.6(a) and (b). For example in Fig. 6(a), for 24 hours of penetration test, penetration depth of Cl element around $x/L \approx 0.36$ from HCl side, where at the same time decreasing of average molecular weight of PA 66 also was observed at 0-0.36 of thickness from HCl side.

Fig. 7 (a) Molecular weight distribution of polyamide 66 along the thickness after permeation test in 10 wt % H_2SO_4 solution (b) Molecular weight degradation at several points of thickness with time interval after permeation test in 10 wt % H_2SO_4 solution

The same result was also observed when we worked with H_2SO_4 solution in our previous works as shown in Fig. 8(a) and (b). In Fig. 8(a), for 72 hours of penetration test, penetration depth of S element around $x/L \approx 0.35$ from H_2SO_4 side, where at the same time decreasing of average molecular weight of PA 66 also reduced at 0-0.35 of thickness from H_2SO_4 side.

Figure 8(b) also shows the same result with Fig. 6(a), Fig. 6(b) and Fig. 8(a). The decrease of molecular weight occurred at the area where anion element was presence. Anion might have contribution to the reaction mechanism. Therefore, anion of acid solution also affected the mechanism of hydrolytic reaction in PA66.

Fig. 8 Relation between penetration depth of S element and average molecular weight distribution of polyamide 66 along the thickness after permeation test in 10 wt % H_2SO_4 solution (a) for 72 hours (b) for 120 hours

Comparison of degradation of molecular weight by acid solution and acid vapor was performed in Fig.6(a) and (b). Figure 6(a) shows the relation between penetration of Cl element and average molecular weight of PA66 after permeation test in 10 wt % HCl solution – water system at 50°C, whereas Fig. 6(b) shows the relation for in vapor of 20 wt % HCl solution – air at 45°C. In this case, we don't discuss about degree of degradation comparison between HCl solution and HCl vapor due to the different of concentration, but we focused on reducing of average molecular weight profile. In Fig.6(a), average molecular weight reduced monotonously as increasing of concentration of Cl element. On the other hand, in Fig.6(b), it shows discontinuous reducing of average molecular weight that follows discontinuous increasing of concentration of Cl element as explained in Fig. 5(b).

Finally, from the knowledge of permeation behavior of the acid solution and vapor into polyamide 66, degradation behavior/mechanism of polyamide or other polymeric material also can be studied.

CONCLUSION

Permeation behavior of acid solution and vapor (HCl) into polyamide 66 showed the different behavior. The differences are not only on its diffusivity into PA66 but also to the distribution of Cl element in PA66. Both of penetration/permeation of acid solution and acid vapor (HCl) into PA66 follow the Fickian diffusion. In this case, diffusion rate of acid solution in liquid phase is faster than that in vapor from the same solution due to high density of liquid and direct contact of liquid phase with PA66. Anion of acid solution takes part in PA66 degradation which related with molecular weight degradation. Degree of degradation depends on the concentration of anion in PA66. Gradation of anion (Cl element) distribution of HCl solution in PA66 was observed monotonously decrease. This trend was also recognized in reducing of PA66 molecular weight, which decreased monotonously with increasing of Cl concentration. On the other hand, concentration gradient of Cl element of HCl vapors in PA66 show discontinuous gradation which also observed in decreasing of PA66 molecular weight.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank UBE Co. for supporting PA66 specimens (UBE 2020B).

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